

Linkages between Outdoor Learning in early years and primary education with recreational visits to the outdoors as young adults: A narrative literature review

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Executive summary

This report considers the potential for linkages between outdoor learning by pre-school and primary age pupils (3-12 year olds) with subsequent recreational visits to the outdoors by secondary school aged children and young adults. Scotland's Curriculum for Excellence seeks to ensure that all children will experience outdoor learning. Given this, an understanding of the impact that outdoor learning has across the life course can assist policymakers in developing effective early years and outdoor education and outdoor learning policy.

We undertook a narrative literature review focusing on research studies primarily conducted in northern Europe and North America. We found little literature that directly addressed our primary research question. However, what we did find suggests that residential outdoor educational experiences in primary school can motivate secondary school aged young people to engage in recreational visits to the outdoors.

Using a life course lens, we draw from the review to report on the known benefits to adults and young people as a result of nature engagement in childhood. We then identify some of the key barriers and constraints, as well as motivators, to young adults making recreational visits to the outdoors. We also report on the dimensions of gender and ethnicity, taking an intersectional approach which recognises the interconnection across multiple characteristics for any one individual. Through an examination of the benefits that have been identified as arising from outdoor learning and outdoor education in practice in early years and primary education, we identify opportunities that may mitigate some of the barriers that prevent young people making recreational use of the outdoors.

Finally, we discuss some of the remaining barriers to equitable outdoor learning for Scotland's young people, and highlight future research recommendations.

Key findings

- There is an overall lack of research across secondary school aged children and young people on motivations for and barriers to using outdoor space, but important factors include:
 - Socially structured exclusion from public outdoor places
 - Past visits with parents to outdoor places, such as forests, and parental attitudes to nature
 - Common interests with peers
 - Perceptions of safety (especially for females) and boredom
- Key capabilities/competencies developed through outdoor learning include:
 - Resilience and problem-solving skills
 - How to behave safely in nature
 - Sharing/conveying knowledge to others
- Development of the skills, knowledge and capabilities to make recreational visits to the outdoors can be supported through:
 - Free play and active engagement with nature through outdoor learning activities
 - Social support through friends with similar outdoor learning experiences

- Familial interest and support, supplemented through ripple effects from educational experiences

Remaining barriers and challenges

We discuss remaining barriers to outdoor learning and outdoor education in Scotland, including:

- Inequity of access: not all schools in Scotland are delivering the same amount of outdoor learning
- Low practitioner confidence in delivering outdoor learning
- Lack of local knowledge about appropriate green spaces to visit
- Missing data about outdoor learning and outdoor education in secondary school education

Future Research Recommendations

We recommend future research is conducted in the following areas:

- Longitudinal research to better understand whether/how outdoor learning in early and primary years education impacts recreational visits to the outdoors in the secondary school age group
- Further research on intersectionality, such as gender, ethnicity and socioeconomic status, as well as the influence of urban and rural locations in which children grow up.

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1. Overview of report

This literature review forms part of a work package within the James Hutton Institute led project titled '*Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing*' (JHI-C6-1) funded by the Scottish Government under the Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services (RESAS) Strategic Research Programme (SRP) 2022-27. An overarching and longstanding interest from Scottish Government is in increasing use of the outdoors and green space. Encouraging, managing and investing in this behaviour has cross-sectoral policy significance relating to planning, environment, health, tourism and education.

The overall aim for the Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing project is to investigate possibilities and constraints for building capacities for reciprocal nature engagement through aspects of environmental settings (type, quality), users (barriers, behaviours), mechanisms for benefit (green prescribing, outdoor learning) and investment (costs, preventative spend). Our use of the language 'reciprocal nature engagement' reflects a move toward a less utilitarian framing of the people-nature connection than might be suggested in phrases such as 'use of the outdoors'.

Discourse suggests that mainstreaming outdoor learning and outdoor education, and ensuring universal access to outdoor settings, has the potential to provide benefits to all school children (O'Brien et al., 2016). Outdoor learning and outdoor education can encourage behavioural change in terms of engagement with nature (Shanahan et al., 2019). This intervention may be particularly important for children who find opportunities for play in natural environments challenging to access. Children are a vulnerable group negatively impacted by a lack of contact with nature (Zwierzchowska & Lupa, 2021). Therefore, providing children access to the natural environment through education (e.g. outdoor learning and outdoor education) could increase their contact and engagement with nature (Smith et al., 2018) in an equitable way. Providing access in this way, could afford all children the same opportunities to engage with the outdoors.

This literature review specifically considers the potential for linkages between outdoor learning by pre-school and primary age pupils with subsequent recreational visits to the outdoors by secondary school age children and young adults (age 12-18). This is important for two reasons. First, because many young people are known to use the outdoors less compared to adults (Oppliger et al., 2019). As such, there is a drop-off phase, in which many young people do not experience the benefits of the outdoors. Therefore, young people are an important group to focus on how to best facilitate and encourage nature engagements. Second, an understanding of the impact that outdoor recreation in childhood has across the life course can assist policymakers in developing early years and outdoor education policy and investment.

The focus on subsequent recreational visits to the outdoors aligns with the Scottish Government's National Performance Framework which aims to get more people outdoors. Here, we are specifically interested in understanding how outdoor learning and outdoor education during early learning and childcare and primary school may be a driver for recreational visits to the outdoors by secondary school aged children and young adults. The interest in getting more people outdoors hinges on the general acceptance of the multiple wellbeing benefits of spending time outdoors, thus, the emphasis is placed on finding ways to get people outdoors. We will discuss relevant factors that influence individuals' observation of, and experience in, natural spaces. These include factors such as age, gender, ethnicity and capabilities of the individual as well as the qualities, opportunities and barriers that various environments and programmatic interventions offer to support (or not) nature engagement.

2. Definitions and Scottish Context

For the purposes of this report, Table 1 provides definitions for the relevant concepts associated with this review, including outdoor learning (OL), outdoor education (OE), the context in which these take place and with whom. These definitions were developed drawing on relevant literature and in consultation with relevant stakeholders.

Table 1. Concepts and definitions used in the review.

Outdoor Learning (OL)	OL is an approach to learning embedded within the curriculum. It takes place in a range of contexts such as the school grounds, local areas, on day excursions or field trips and residential experiences. Its purposes include developing environmental understanding, encouraging physical activity, health and wellbeing, and personal and social development (Education-Scotland, 2015).
Outdoor Education (OE)	OE is a distinct field of study on which educational programmes have been based since the mid-1900s. OE has been, and still is, within the purview of informal education providers and is based on shorter term, supplementary learning experiences to a student's formal schooling (Miller, 2017).
Forest School	Forest School is an early example of OE and OL in the UK, established in the 1990's. This approach was developed following a visit to Denmark by a team of Early Years Professionals from Bridgewater College, Somerset, England, who subsequently established a similar version in their area (Turtle et al., 2015; O'Brien & Murray, 2007; Trapasso et al., 2018). The group worked with other staff throughout the UK to support them in setting up their own Forest School. In Scotland, the Forest Kindergarten programme models a Forest School approach for early years education.
Early learning and childcare (ELC)	"Early learning and childcare" refers to a service, consisting of education and care, of a kind which is suitable in the ordinary case for children who are under school age, with regard being had to the importance of interactions and other experiences which support learning and development in a caring and nurturing setting (in Section 46 of Children and Young People (Scotland) Act 2014).
Context in which the intervention may take place	
Green space	<i>Vegetated areas and blue spaces</i> in both urban and rural areas, including woodland, parks, farmland, paths, and beaches and other aquatic environments that are publicly accessible (Scottish Government, 2018).
Nature	We use the term nature to include people's interactions with the environment from the countryside and rural areas through to urban green spaces in heavily populated areas, and gardens or green spaces within school grounds (O'Brien et al., 2011).
Visits to the outdoors	We operationalise visits to the outdoors per the National Performance Indicator as both everyday activities done from home or while on a Scotland-based holiday.
With whom	
Pre-school / school age children/ young adults	<p>Early Learning and Childcare: Children in Scotland can attend a local authority nursery or a partner provider service from the age of 3.</p> <p>Primary school: Dependent on when in the year a child's birthday falls, children will attend primary school for seven years between the ages of 5 and 12.</p> <p>Secondary school: Dependent on when in the year a child's birthday falls, children will attend secondary school for up to six years between the ages of 12 and 18.</p>

Since 2006 Scotland has moved towards an education curriculum that requires outdoor learning to be a regular and progressive experience for all learners, from 3-18 years (<https://ftl.org.uk/key-policies-scotland/>). The vision for the future was one where Scotland's education curriculum would offer real-world learning experiences outdoors, where the outdoor 'classroom' could be found not only in the school grounds but in diverse outdoor locations (e.g. local green spaces, forests, wild spaces) and for different time frames (e.g. brief outdoor visits, full day, residential trips). The 2007 publication [Taking Learning Outdoors](#) defined the *outdoor classroom* as a setting, *outdoor education* as a process in which educators, students and others take part, and *outdoor learning* as the learning which accrues as a result.

There is a recognition that OL goes hand in hand with play, and this is enshrined in Scotland's National Outdoor Play and Learning position statement: "We will work together to embed playing and learning outdoors as an everyday activity and we will celebrate it as a fundamental part of growing up in Scotland" (Inspiring Scotland, 2018, p.9). The Scottish Government's Play Strategy (currently being updated) cites the need for children and young people to have daily free play opportunities in natural spaces.

Through OL, it is envisaged that the four capacities of the Curriculum for Excellence (Scottish Government, 2010) can be supported: developing successful learners, confident individuals, responsible citizens and effective contributors. Learning outdoors is now firmly embedded in the CfE (Curriculum for Excellence through Outdoor Learning, 2010) and is also a key component within the Scottish Government's broader cross-curricular approach, Learning for Sustainability (Scottish Government, 2012). Learning for Sustainability (LfS) aims to enable learners, educators, schools and their wider communities to build a socially just, sustainable and equitable society. As such, an effective whole-school and community approach to LfS weaves together global citizenship, sustainable development education and outdoor learning to create coherent, rewarding and transformative learning experiences.

A recent report (Successful Approaches to Learning Outdoors, 2022) provided a positive assessment of OL, highlighting examples of effective practice at different ages and stages of education across Scotland. Yet, a report commissioned by NatureScot (Mannion et al., 2023) found that while time spent outdoors has increased in ELC settings since 2014, there has been a decrease in average amount of time spent outdoors in the primary school sector. The authors note that there is a need to increase teacher confidence and expertise, via high quality professional learning, in order to meet the required expansion of OL and play. Thus, there remain challenges to delivering the successful and impactful OL envisaged within the LfS Vision2030+ (Scottish Government, 2016).

Scotland is recognised by other countries as an early leader in outdoor learning, and its situation within the LfS policy context is globally unique (Christie & Higgins, 2020). There is a wealth of shared resources available to practitioners and teachers to support the delivery of OL and LfS. Some examples include:

- An [online library](#) of OL resources. This contains examples of case studies in Scotland that include early learning and childcare, primary school and secondary school evidence. Further, it provides learning policies and documents, COVID-related guidance, professional learning, research documents and webinars. (<https://education.gov.scot/resources/a-summary-of-outdoor-learning-resources/>)
- [Interactive map](#) of OL and play providers in Scotland (<https://nnolscotland.blogspot.com/2020/08/map-of-outdoor-learning-and-play.html>)
- [OL directory for Scotland](#) (<https://outdoorlearningdirectory.com/>)

- [Summary of Learning for Sustainability resources](https://education.gov.scot/resources/a-summary-of-learning-for-sustainability-resources/)
(<https://education.gov.scot/resources/a-summary-of-learning-for-sustainability-resources/>)

Critically for the success of OL and OE, within Scotland as well as more broadly, is the need for engagement from different stakeholders at different levels. This input is necessary from public, private and third-sector organisations (see Table 2).

- **Table 2.** Scottish stakeholder engagement and input (Information adapted from Learning and Teaching Scotland, 2010).

Stakeholder level	Engagement and input
National-level engagement from government bodies and national agencies	To provide expertise and support continued professional development (CPD) for staff to deliver outdoor experiences. Strives to assist a coordinated approach, maximising resources in CPD, research and quality assurance for outdoor learning and outdoor education.
Local authority level	Some local authorities in Scotland have a designated officer specifically for outdoor learning. They work to spearhead strategic planning across services to build on an authority-wide plan for young people to have access to good quality outdoor learning experiences.
Cluster and community level	Work to develop networks that share resources and knowledge.
Organisational level	Organisations work to review the Curriculum for Excellence to plan their outdoor learning and outdoor education opportunities that work for their environment.
Individual level	Individuals who are directly responsible for learning are considered the best placed to deliver the teaching and learning experiences. Individuals work to design lessons that suit their environment and the curriculum requirements.

3. Methods

3.1 Literature Search

Our narrative literature synthesis followed a two-phase approach to identify and review relevant literature (see Appendix 1).

Phase 1: Primary review

Search strategy and information sources: We conducted a Boolean search using a combination of keywords (see Table 3) with AND/OR to search for literature using the Web of Science database (all databases, selected for the breadth of publications across the social sciences). The keywords were agreed with relevant stakeholders from the Scottish Government. We incorporated parameters in our search strategy, which include: (i) the publication status (published peer-reviewed and grey literature, excluding pre-prints); (ii) type of source (primary, secondary, review, excluding editorial or opinion pieces); (iii) study design

(to include qualitative and quantitative research with a key interest on longitudinal prospective or retrospective research); and (iv) English-language. We placed no restrictions on publication year to ensure identification of relevant seminal work and longitudinal studies that may have been published over time.

Table 3. Concept and associated search string used in the Web of Science.

Concept area	Keywords
Outdoor learning/ education	forest school OR forest kindergarten OR outdoor education OR outdoor learning OR residential experiences OR fieldtrips OR outdoor education centres OR outdoor nursery OR outdoor play and learning
Visits to the outdoors	nature engage* OR “use of outdoors” OR “visits to outdoors” OR “outdoor recreation” OR “outdoor leisure”

Selection process: Our initial search identified 1,318 records. Paper titles and abstracts were split between 3 co-authors and screened to exclude duplicates, pre-prints, editorial, opinion piece, non-English. Additional criteria were used to identify literature relevant to the Scottish context and the primary research context i.e. that they are focused on either education or recreation time.

Narrative synthesis process: The full text of the remaining 98 records was then read (by 4 co-authors) to extract information under the following categories: benefits, barriers, opportunities, capabilities, gender and ethnicity. Each of these terms is defined in Table 4 (see next page). In addition, we noted knowledge gaps identified by the authors. 30 records were removed due to lack of relevance, leaving 68 records. We thematically analysed the extracted information to generate insight into the research question and identify any gaps to be addressed through a targeted review.

Phase 2: Targeted review

This phase sought to identify material specifically focused on 12 to 18 year-olds’ recreational use of the outdoors. We used four search strategies to identify literature: (i) targeted grey literature search; (ii) targeted journal search (iii) targeted scholar search; and (iv) articles which were identified in the references of literature from the primary review.

Using the same keywords from the primary review to search grey literature, we searched the websites of: NatureScot, Greenspace Scotland, Forest Research, Woodland Trust, Education Scotland, Learning for Sustainability, Public Health Scotland, National Trust Scotland, Scottish Forestry and Edinburgh University Centre for Environmental Education. We then targeted two key relevant journals, namely *Environmental Education Research* and *Journal of Outdoor Recreation and Tourism*. The scholars that we targeted included: Catherine Ward Thompson, Alexia Barrable, Louise Chawla and Liz O’Brien. This phase 2 process identified an additional 33 documents for review. The additional documents were assessed for inclusion using the same selection criteria as for the primary review, except for geographic scope, which we broadened. 33 resulting documents were subjected to full-text review using the same extraction themes as in the primary review to inform this report. This resulted in a total of 93 full-text reviews which have informed this report.

Table 4. Definitions of terms used in literature synthesis.

Term	Definition
Benefits	The benefits mentioned in this report are broad ranging. Dillon et al. (2005, p. 22) discuss the benefits of outdoor experiences under four headings: Cognitive impacts – concerning knowledge, understanding and other academic outcomes. Affective impacts – encompassing attitudes, values, beliefs and self-perceptions. Interpersonal/social impacts – including communication skills, leadership and teamwork. Physical/behavioural impacts – relating to physical fitness, physical skills, personal behaviours and social actions. This report also includes a fifth category as the wider benefits that ripple into family and home life.
Barriers	Barriers are the constraints – physical or social – that prevent behaviours taking place. In this report we focus primarily on the factors that discourage secondary school age and young adults from making recreational visits to the outdoors. In the discussion (Section 5) we refer to barriers to OL that are encountered by educational practitioners.
Opportunities	Michie et al.’s (2011) model of behaviour change defines opportunity “as all the factors that lie outside the individual that make the behaviour possible or prompt” (p. 4). For the purpose of this report, the behaviour is recreational visits to the outdoors by secondary school aged children and young adults.
Capabilities	Michie et al.’s (2011) model of behaviour change defines capability “as the individual’s psychological and physical capacity to engage in the activity concerned. It includes having the necessary knowledge and skills” (p. 4). For the purpose of this report, the behaviour is recreational visits to the outdoors by secondary school aged children and young adults.
Sex/gender	Whilst we recognise sex as a biological characteristic and gender as a social one, the research does not always distinguish between sex and gender. For the purpose of this report, the focus is on the social characteristics of gender.
Race/ethnicity	Similar to the above, we recognise race as a biological characteristic and ethnicity as a social one, yet the literature reviewed is not always clear as to which the focus is concerned. For the purpose of this report, our focus is on the social characteristics of ethnicity.

3.2 Framing the findings: a life course perspective

Researchers note that one of the limitations of research in children’s experiences of nature is the tendency to deem childhood as a uniform experience and to limit experience to a single point in time (Izenstark & Middaugh, 2022). This observation is reflected in the findings from our literature search: the majority of our identified studies that focus on investigating the effects of OL and OE measure and assess impacts over the immediate or relatively short term (weeks to months) rather than over a longer life course term (see Tables in Appendix 2). As such, this

review incorporates a life course lens to attempt to place the knowledge gleaned about OL and OE into the context of the individual's life.

The life course perspective is an interdisciplinary research paradigm that considers the temporal context of behaviour. Elder and Giele (1998), some of the early pioneers in this area of research, defined life course as "...a sequence of socially defined events and roles that the individual enacts over time" (Elder & Giele, 1998 p. 22). Life course perspective therefore takes a developmental approach, and examines individuals' roles and experiences throughout their life, whilst drawing importance from points of transition that mark shifts in these roles or states over the lifespan (Elder et al., 2003; Colley et al., 2019). Through this lens Izenstark and Middaugh (2022) highlight the importance of children's exposure to nature and acknowledge the developmental benefits that are evident in adulthood, as has been detailed within the wider literature (see Wells & Lekies, 2006; Chawla, 2007; Ward Thompson et al., 2008) (see Section 4.1).

4. Results

An overview of the key academic journal papers identified in our review is provided in Appendix 2. We have grouped the references according to the location in which they were conducted (UK or elsewhere) and whether they were studies based on an educational intervention or not.

Our literature search identified only one study that specifically examined linkages between OL and OE in primary education with recreational visits to the outdoors by secondary school aged children and young adults. Liddicoat and Krasny (2014) conducted qualitative interviews with 54 teenagers five years after they had taken part in residential OE programmes (lasting 3 days) in the United States, to find out how the participants felt their experience had impacted them. Some participants reported their experience had encouraged them to hike and camp more, and for those that already took part in such activities with their families, the experience encouraged them to engage with nature in a more thoughtful and careful manner. Although we found additional literature that supports this autobiographical memory link between OE experiences in childhood and later pro-environmental careers and attitudes (e.g. Broom, 2017; Gray & Piggott, 2018), this is the only study we identified that reported a direct link between a primary school level OE experience with recreational visits to the outdoors by secondary school-aged young people (in this case 15-18 years old).

Despite the lack of further evidence in the literature addressing our research question directly, there is insight to be gleaned from the literature that discusses current barriers to and motivation for young people's recreational engagement with the outdoors (see Section 4.3). There is also useful insight from the literature that can help inform our understanding of how OE and OL can help young people to develop the capabilities that could potentially increase their recreational visits to the outdoors (see Section 4.6).

Although our research interest is focused particularly on secondary school aged children, in this report we consider findings from the wider life course context (see Section 3.2). Before discussing the findings relating to secondary school aged children, we provide a brief overview of the links between adult nature behaviour/experience and their experience of nature engagement during childhood. We begin with adults as there is a more established body of literature on the linkages between them and their childhood experiences.

4.1 Adults and their childhood nature experiences

There is limited evidence in the literature identified in our review on the long-term effects of OL and OE in younger years for adults. This is primarily due to a lack of longitudinal research studies following children and their school experiences through to adulthood. There is, however, informative evidence about the long-term benefits of spending time in nature as a child. The literature suggests that nature engagement in childhood positively affects adult wellbeing, activity and attitudes, but that it is more immersive experiences in 'wild nature' as a child that are most likely to result in long-term attitude and behavioural effects.

Multiple studies have found that the experiences that children have in natural areas, such as woods and forests, increase the likelihood of return visits in adulthood (e.g. Wells & Lekies, 2006; Ward-Thompson et al., 2002; Ward-Thompson, 2008; Taye et al., 2019). Conversely, research has found that where children did not frequent outdoor green spaces, they are less likely to visit these spaces as adults (e.g. Hegetschweiler, 2022; Vitale et al., 2022).

Wellbeing (physical and mental)

By the time they leave secondary school, young people's attitudes to exercise and physical activity are predictive of adult physical activity levels (McNamee, 2017; O'Brien et al., 2016). The RSPB report *Every Child Outdoors* (2010) states that 'the strongest relationship is with the quality of exercise they have experienced, as opposed to the quantity of exercise. Nature is a major motivating factor for exercise' (p.6). Furthermore, performing physical activity in an outdoor environment reduces the risk of developing chronic illness (Strong et al., 2005 cited in Sgro et al., 2021).

Through questionnaires distributed across different parts of the UK, Ward-Thompson et al. (2008) reported that people who visited green places as children are more likely to visit, as an adult, similar areas within walking distance of home; this suggests a link between childhood outdoor exercise and adult behaviour. Additionally, there is much evidence that spending time in nature as a child is linked to better subjective wellbeing and lower risk of poor mental health during both childhood and adulthood (see Vitale et al., 2022).

Attitudes, values and actions as adults

There is evidence that adult nature connection and environmental stewardship may have their roots in childhood (e.g. Barrable & Booth, 2020; Well & Lekies, 2006; Christie & Higgins, 2020). Children who free play in wild natural environments are more likely to demonstrate pro-environmental behaviours and attitudes as adults (Education Scotland, 2009), as are those who hike, camp and go orienteering (Sgro et al., 2021; Wells & Lekies, 2006).

There is an indicative link between the environmental careers that adults may choose to pursue and their nature experiences in childhood (Turtle et al., 2015; Well & Lekies, 2006; Chawla, 2006, Prevot et al., 2018). Frequently, the nature experiences that these adults report having had in childhood tend to be particularly rich, and often involve intense or residential activities in wild or untended nature, often through structured OE programmes or clubs, such as scouts (Well & Lekies, 2006). For example, following up with participants of a 2-year nature-immersive curriculum in an Australian high school 30 years later, Gray and Piggott (2018) found many of them employed in environmental, conservation and outdoor leadership roles.

4.2 Young people and the impact of childhood Outdoor Learning and Outdoor Education

Although not addressing recreational visits to the outdoors specifically, there is evidence of the impact that OE and OL has on young people.

OL and OE contributes to increased environmental knowledge on topics such as biodiversity (Christie & Higgins, 2020; Taylor, 2022; Wells & Lekies, 2006), and this increase in understanding has been linked to a higher environmental concern and environmentally responsible behaviours observed amongst teenagers (Liddicoat & Krasny, 2014; Prevot et al., 2018). Taylor (2022) suggests that environmental education trains young people for environmental stewardship. Time spent outdoors as a child is identified in several studies to strengthen young people's later environmental identity, leading to individuals feeling more connected to the natural environment and eliciting an emotional response to environmental issues (Prevot et al., 2018). In one study, young environmental leaders (aged 16-19) highlighted experiences with nature in their younger years as influential in their pro-environmental choices (Arnold et al., 2009, cited in Prevot et al., 2018). OE and nature-based learning and activities have also been found to have positive impacts on academic learning on subjects unrelated to the outdoors (Christie & Higgins 2020).

Development of personal and social skills

Teenage years are an important period for personal development. In one of the few studies we identified that undertook a longer term investigation of the benefits of OL, Hartmeyer and Mygind (2016) conducted interviews with teenagers five years after they had completed a 3-year programme where they were taught outside one day per week (aged 9-11). Participants were observed to have stronger cooperation skills compared to students who had not been taught outside.

Educational outdoor field trips are a particularly rich opportunity for students to develop self-esteem and social skills. During such trips they face challenges and are encouraged to find solutions both independently and through cooperation with their peers. The impacts from residential field trips have been found to have lasting effects (Liddicoat & Krasny, 2014; Gregg, 2009). Teenage environmental leaders cite natural experiences during childhood as influential, suggesting that OL and OE may provide young people with the drive to become leaders in environmental movements (Prevot et al., 2018).

4.3 Young people – what drives recreational visits to the outdoors?

It is widely acknowledged that there is a 'teenage dip' in young people's engagement in outdoor activities, especially in the early teenage years (Richardson et al., 2019), which coincides with many developmental changes as young people develop their self-identity and prioritise social relationships. Through our literature search we identified a number of factors that can (de)motivate young people in making recreational visits to the outdoors (see Figure 1, next page).

Figure 1. Factors that affect young people’s visits to the outdoors

External and internal perceptions of teenagers in public outdoor spaces

External perceptions affect young people’s recreational visits to the outdoors; adults often hold negative views of teenagers’ presence in public outdoor spaces (Ward-Thompson, 2008). In fact, evidence has identified ‘socially structured exclusion’ of particular groups, including teenagers, from outdoor activities (Ward-Thompson, 2008). Safety is another prevalent component when young people engage in outdoor visits without adult supervision. Young people have highlighted that the presence of other teenagers in outdoor spaces can generate feelings of vulnerability, and fear of being attacked or robbed are significant concerns when it comes to spending time outdoors (Ward-Thompson, 2008; Oppliger et al., 2019). Gender can also come into play in relation to the safety factor: male teenagers are more likely to use outdoor spaces than females (Hegetschweiler et al., 2022), while female young people report feeling less safe than their male counterparts (Girlguiding, 2020; Make Space for Girls, 2023).

Parental/familial influence

Izenstark and Middaugh (2022) identified that frequent family-based nature activities throughout childhood (particularly between 7 and 17 years) increases the likelihood of a preference for spending recreational time outdoors in emerging adulthood (18-25 years). Similarly, Oppliger et al. (2019) surveyed 643 Swiss adolescents between the ages of 13 and 22 on their recreational use of forests. They found that one of the strongest predictors of recreational forest use by Swiss young people was the number of past visits with parents, and hypothesise that these visits enable parents to pass on their attitudes to the outdoors to their children, at the same time as developing their children’s familiarity with outdoor spaces. If parents do not visit with their children, this can then become a constraint on young people’s future visits, meaning that parental attitudes can be both a positive and negative influence on young people’s future recreational use of the outdoors.

Oppliger et al. (2019) also found that forest visits are widely viewed as a family activity. This can mean that young people can feel too old to visit with their parents and simultaneously feel too young, as they do not yet have partners/children of their own with whom to visit.

Social support

Socialising is frequently cited as the main reason that young people choose to spend time outdoors, and therefore the impact of peer preferences are likely to be very influential in this age bracket (Hegetschweiler, 2022; Prevot et al., 2018). Respondents in Oppliger's (2019) study reported a key constraint to visiting forests was friends not liking to visit. It has been suggested that without social support, strong environmental identity and pro-environmental behaviours may be difficult to maintain (Prevot et al., 2018).

'Boring and disgusting'

Oppliger et al. (2019) argue that many young people have lost the ability to self-entertain due to the ubiquity of electronic media, and that higher electronic media use is associated with a perception of outdoor settings, such as woodlands, as boring to visit. Young people further report being put off visiting forests due to dirt. In a 2020 report on children's access to adventure and play, the Girlguiding Organisation reported that a fifth of their sample of over 1000 children said their worry about getting dirty or messy outdoors, but by the time they are 15-18, this figure increases to 33% for girls and 23% for boys. Young people are also discouraged by the presence of insects such as ticks and mosquitos (Oppliger et al., 2019).

These negative feelings are shown to decrease if participants visit during childhood and are encouraged to engage in free play which can help familiarise them to these unfamiliar spaces (Alme & Reime, 2021; Trapasso et al., 2018; Education Scotland, 2009; Oppliger et al., 2019). This suggests a tangible positive influence of childhood visits to young people's attitudes and behaviours toward the outdoors.

4.4 Benefits from Outdoor Learning and Outdoor Education during Early Learning and Childcare and primary school

As observed by Christie and Higgins (2020) in their review of the educational outcomes of Scotland's LfS, there is much emerging evidence that learning outdoors has a positive impact on learning. Academic learning can be boosted through outdoor learning, including in subjects unrelated to the outdoor context. The authors also point to evidence for additional benefits to health, wellbeing and confidence of young people.

In this section we discuss the benefits that have been demonstrated to arise from OL and OE during ELC and primary school.

We identified several wide-reaching benefits that are evident through participating in OL or OE during ELC and primary school (3-12 year olds). The benefits are discussed in terms of the themes identified by Dillon et al. (2005, p 22): interpersonal and social impacts, physical and behavioural impacts, affective impacts and cognitive impacts (see Table 5). Benefits are not discussed in order of importance, as their importance will depend on the individual.

We also include a fifth category of our own, that of the wider impacts that ripple into family and home life.

Table 5. Immediate benefits associated with Outdoor Learning and Outdoor Education.

Theme	Associated benefits identified
<p>Interpersonal and social impacts</p> <p>Including communication skills, leadership and teamwork</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased learning and attainment • Improved risk management • Enhanced social skills • Improved group working abilities
<p>Physical and behavioural impacts</p> <p>Relating to physical fitness, physical skills, personal behaviours and social actions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical health benefits • Physical and motor skill development
<p>Affective impacts</p> <p>Encompassing attitudes, values, beliefs and self-perceptions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emotional wellbeing benefits • More likely to have pro-environmental behaviours
<p>Cognitive impacts</p> <p>Concerning knowledge, understanding and other academic outcomes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Beneficial to those with Attention Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) • Feeling connected to nature / forming a positive relationship to nature
<p>Wider impact</p> <p>Concerning pro-environmental behaviours/behaviour change and ripple effects into home life</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A desire to act differently in future • Ripple effect into home, family life and beyond

Interpersonal and social impacts

OL and OE have noticeable benefits for different learning experiences across the curriculum. The language and communication skills of children attending forest school are noted to improve, particularly regarding vocabulary and use of descriptive language, which is attributed to forest school enabling interaction with older students as well as exposure to natural elements, such as fauna and flora terminology (Smith et al., 2018; Turtle et al., 2015; O'Brien & Murray, 2007).

Engaging in OE and OL can improve students' self-esteem and self-confidence (Alme & Reime, 2021; Turtle et al., 2015; Gregg, 2009). Natural environments are believed to be a particularly good context for the emergence of informal and unplanned learning situations (Alme & Reime, 2021). These situations encourage students to learn democratic values, such as respect for others whilst learning together (Aasen et al., 2009 cited in Alme & Reime, 2021). Students are also noted to develop leadership skills through taking part in outdoor activities (Alme & Reime, 2021; Gregg, 2009). As well as increasing personal social skills, OL and OE have been demonstrated to improve children's ability to work collaboratively as a group (Mann et al., 2022; Hartmeyer & Mygind, 2016; Alme & Reime, 2021; Gregg, 2009). Gregg (2009) discusses the results of residential OE programmes, noting that by spending time together in a different environment, children improve their conflict resolution skills and that these experiences help with group cohesion and cooperation. In Scotland it is common for children to attend a residential outdoor education centre in their final year of primary school, and the

benefits from this experience include increasing self-esteem, confidence and resilience (Outdoor Learning, 2011).

Physical and behavioural impacts

The physical health benefits of nature exposure for children are expansive. In their systematic review, Martin et al. (2020) report that children are typically less sedentary in OL environments than in the classroom. There is agreement within the literature that outdoor activities are important for children's physical skills and motor development, including increased stamina and better balance (Traynor et al., 2022; Alme & Reime, 2021; Saaklahti & Niemisto, 2021; Turtle et al., 2015; O'Brien & Murray, 2007). Puhakka et al. (2019) observe there are potential benefits to children's immune systems through the microbial diversity to be found in outdoor school learning environments, and research in Australia found short-sightedness in 6 and 7 years olds was positively affected by outdoor time (Education Scotland, 2009).

Through spending time outdoors during OL and OE, children gain confidence via a variety of activities, such as building dens and climbing trees. and learn to take managed risks (Trapasso et al., 2018; O'Brien & Murray, 2007), for example in learning to observe rules around a fire area (O'Brien & Murray, 2007). Children also are exposed to inclement weather which can help build resilience and understanding of how to play and engage with nature in a range of conditions (Saaklahti & Niemisto, 2021).

Affective impacts

The literature highlights affective benefits for children who spend time in OE. Garip et al. (2021) found that almost all children that participated in their nature programmes reported feeling positive and were observed to have restorative experiences whilst in green space. Children used positive terms to express how the spaces made them feel, including "happy", "joyful" and "amazed". These positive feelings are echoed by a study by Trapasso et al. (2018) in which children stated that forest school positively influenced their mood, making them feel happier. They noted that this increased happiness is thought to be due to the natural environment, along with the behaviours it encourages, such as free play, creativity, social interaction and increased exercise. As well as feeling more positive and happier, Harvey et al. (2020) discussed that access to green space in school grounds reduced students' stress levels and improved memory and attention restoration.

Learning experiences conducted in natural environments are thought to encourage a greater awareness of environmental issues, foster empathy towards the natural environment, and develop a concern for the protection of the environment (Turtle et al., 2015; Spencer & Nelson, 1994; O'Brien & Murray, 2007). Garip et al. (2021) found that after participating in their nature programme, participants felt a sense of responsibility to protect green spaces for the future.

Cognitive impacts

Studies have noted that children's motivation to learn improves (Goldstein et al., 2019; Puhakka et al., 2019; Smith et al., 2018), students are seen to take ownership over their learning (Mann et al., 2022) and improve their concentration (Turtle et al., 2015). Nature is seen to promote a calmer, quieter and safer context for learning and to contribute to developing attentional skills (Alme & Reime, 2021).

While spending time in OE and OL is beneficial to all learners, it may be of particular benefit to students with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) and other additional support needs. Children with ADHD function better after activities in green settings, displaying improved concentration after time spent outdoors (Education Scotland 2009; O'Brien et al., 2011). OE and OL may therefore serve as a new tool in the toolkit for managing ADHD

symptoms and other additional support needs (Education Scotland, 2009; O'Brien et al., 2016).

Repeated contact with nature in an educational context appears to increase feelings of nature connection (see Barrable & Booth, 2020). In a quantitative study, Garip et al. (2021) analysed data from 16 schools with a total sample of 504 students. They found that participating in nature programmes significantly improved children's before and after ratings on a range of outcomes, including their feeling of nature connection. Ayotte-Beaudet et al. (2021) interviewed 63 primary school students after three outdoor science lessons and found their participants' connection to nature evolved, as did their desire to protect it.

Wider impact: the ripple effect

Research suggests that OL and OE can have a ripple effect into the home and family life (Smith et al., 2018; O'Brien & Murray, 2007). Children are reported to copy activities that they have learned during OL, such as hunting for bugs, in their own gardens (Smith et al., 2018). Similarly, White (2018) found that after participating in their school-based birdwatching programme, children stated that they wanted to continue feeding and surveying birds and engage in bird activities whilst at home.

A key ripple effect of forest School is that students want to take their parents, siblings and extended families out to a woodland or forest school site during weekends and holidays (O'Brien & Murray, 2007; Trapasso et al., 2018; Education Scotland, 2009). This ripple effect can particularly benefit black and minority ethnic (BAME) households with children partaking in OL or in forest school. In the UK, the most cited barrier to BAME adults using green space is lack of knowledge, specifically: lack of general knowledge about available outdoor spaces (Natural England, 2013); lack of knowledge of transport, where to go and what to do when you're there (Ipsos Mori, 2021; The Countryside Charity, 2021; Morris, 2011); and not knowing what the benefits are of spending time outdoors (Ipsos Mori, 2021). Lack of familiarity with outdoor environments is also cited as a key barrier (Edwards, 2021) and Asian communities specifically mention a lack of confidence about spending time outdoors (SRUC, 2021). As such, when BAME families or households have children participating in OL and OE, the ripple effect has the potential to mitigate some of their fear of the unknown and encourage both children and their families to spend time outdoors outwith the school environment.

We further discuss the ripple effect as an opportunity for promoting recreational visits to the outdoors in Section 4.7.

4.5 Intersectionality

When reviewing the literature, intersectionality and the impact this may have on children's involvement in OE and recreational visits to the outdoors was highlighted. Intersectionality of ethnicity and gender were taken into account. As detailed in the methods section, not all the research reviewed distinguished ethnicity from race or gender from sex. For the purpose of our review, we are focused on the social characteristics of children and young people and thus consider ethnicity and gender.

From the evidence collected in this literature review, children and young people residing in lower socioeconomic, urban areas are more likely to have difficulties in accessing outdoor space (The Countryside Charity, 2021; Beyer et al., 2015). When the children or young people from these areas are an ethnic minority, it amplifies these difficulties (Beyer et al., 2015). However, evidence from this literature review suggests that Scotland's commitment to OL and OE may help counteract some of these challenges.

4.5.1 Ethnicity

Black and minority ethnic populations are less likely to be frequent users of green space (Boyd et al, 2018; Tardona et al, 2014). Factors such as gender, socioeconomic class and age can additionally negatively impact these groups' desire to access outdoor spaces (The Countryside Charity, 2021).

When detailing barriers to engaging in outdoor play, Beyer et al. (2015) highlighted that it can be difficult, particularly in urban areas, to access local natural spaces, and that this is especially challenging for ethnic minority children who grow up in urban settings. In addition to lack of access to natural areas, parental concern for safety has been shown to limit children's knowledge of and engagement with nature. Due to the nature of these barriers, the outcome is that children from lower socioeconomic and urban areas will be less likely to engage in play outdoors – children from these areas are also more likely to be children of colour (Beyer et al., 2015). Children from ethnically diverse, lower-income communities in urban areas have less opportunity to engage with outdoor science lessons (Bruyere et al., 2012; Goldstein et al., 2019). Similar to the barrier of parental concern, this can, in part, be attributed to the educators in these settings questioning the appropriateness of urban outdoor areas as places to learn about nature and the environment (Simmons, 1998; Bruyere et al., 2012; Goldstein et al., 2019).

4.5.2 Gender

Gender roles more inclusive and dynamic outside than in the classroom

Research has shown that time spent in OL or ELC settings can afford more creative free play, which in turn encourages more inclusive play for children of different genders, ages and abilities than in more sterile environments (Puhakka et al., 2019; Trapasso et al., 2018). Inclusivity in terms of gender is observed through the reduction or disappearance of traditional gender roles in free play outdoors, when the rules are created by the children themselves and play is naturally more dynamic (Alme & Reime, 2021).

Gender preferences for outdoor activities

Trapasso et al.'s (2018) study investigating differences in children's activity during forest school lessons found that although their dislikes were the same (namely "the natural elements"), boys and girls reported liking different aspects of the class time outdoors. The girls liked the social and creative elements of forest school, as well as the games they got to play, while the boys liked making a fire, the active elements of forest school and the construction activities. In relation to gender roles, and in comparison to Alme and Reime's (2021) research detailing that free play produces less prominent gender roles, Trapasso et al.'s (2018) study demonstrates that when there are set activities, preference for activities related to children's respective gender roles remains.

Effect of gender on physical activity

Our literature review revealed mixed results when examining if gender had a positive or negative effect on involvement in OL and OE. Martin et al. (2022) conducted a systematic review investigating the relationship between childcare environment and children's physical activity time and inactive time. The systematic review found only one study concerning engagement in indoor versus outdoor play, while five studies were identified comparing gender differences in time spent indoors and outdoors. Of the five indoor versus outdoor time studies, four observed that girls were less physically active than boys outdoors and that the increase in physical activity outdoors from indoors was greater for boys. However, Martin et al.'s 2022 review reported variation in gender differences geographically; in North America girls were

reported to be less active outdoors, while in Scandinavian countries the level of activity outdoors was more equal and sometimes girls' physical activity was higher than that of the boys.

Although there are mixed results on girls' and boys' comparative time spent engaging in outdoor play and physical activity, both genders' active time outdoors declines throughout their adolescence. It is worth noting that prior to this decline in adolescence, a higher proportion of boys (approximately 10%) reportedly engage in an hour a day of mild-vigorous activity than girls do (Trapasso et al., 2018). Therefore, the general decline of time spent outdoors for all adolescents will result in fewer girls than boys spending time outside engaging in activities.

4.6 Overcoming barriers to recreational visits to the outdoors

In this section we consider the findings from our literature review with respect to how some of the barriers and constraints to recreational use of the outdoors by young people (as identified in Sections 4.3 and 4.5) can be addressed.

We frame this discussion in terms of opportunities and capabilities (after Michie et al., 2011). Opportunities refer to external factors (both physical and social) provided by the environment that enable a behaviour to be enacted, while capabilities refer to whether individuals have the relevant psychological knowledge and physical abilities to engage in a behaviour (Michie et al., 2011). In this context, the opportunities are provided through the physical and social environment that children encounter through OL and OE at school. Capabilities such as the knowledge of how to behave in the face of inclement weather and biting insects, or how to light and extinguish a fire safely, are the resulting skills.

While the literature we reviewed did not return a great deal of evidence for direct linkages between OL and OE and in ELC and primary school and subsequent recreational visits, it can be argued that some capabilities for recreational outdoor engagement by young people can be developed and afforded through ELC and school-based OL and OE experiences.

Free play

The benefits of free play within OL can be long-lasting. Five years after completing a three-year one day a week 'nature class', Hartmeyer and Mygind (2016) reported participants continued to actively play (as opposed to 'hang around') at a higher age than pupils in other classes in school.

That the play is active and relatively unstructured is important: studies that found no correlation between OE and time in nature state that this is likely because of a focus on structured OE that does not allow for active engagement with nature (Oppliger et al., 2019; Wells & Lekies, 2006). Oppliger et al. (2019) suggested that to encourage teenagers to use forests more often, there needs to be an increase in OL programmes that offer 'engaging forest activities' for young people. It is therefore important that free play is not only encouraged in the ELC and primary school years, but that opportunities are provided within secondary school education too.

Allowing children the freedom for independent play and interaction with nature has been shown to be a key factor in reducing negative perceptions of the outdoors (e.g. O'Brien & Murray, 2007; Zwierzchowska & Lupa, 2021). Opportunities for free play will also familiarise young people with the inclement weather, dirt and insects that are common to outdoor environments, and help to build resilience to these. Learning to deal with these within a school

context should enable the young people to develop the capabilities to visit outdoor environments recreationally.

Social aspects

Socialising and meeting up with friends is of prime importance to young people, and the literature indicates that if young people do not share an enthusiasm for outdoor environments then they are unlikely to visit them together (Oppliger et al., 2019; Prevot et al., 2018). Opportunities for OL and OE at school can facilitate an equity of access to outdoor environments that may be lacking in young people's home lives, and thus has the potential to increase the capabilities of more young people to engage in social activities in outdoor environments. Exposure to OL and OE at school may also reduce the perception in young people that outdoor environments are boring, as the literature finds that in general children respond very positively to OL and OE experiences (e.g. Garip et al., 2021).

Residential OE trips are likely to be particularly useful in developing these capabilities, as are the opportunities provided through partnership organisations and award systems (e.g. John Muir Award, Duke of Edinburgh's Award).

Family

Recreational visits to the outdoors are often undertaken as a family activity, and this activity in younger age groups has been shown to promote recreational visits in young adults (Izenstark & Middaugh, 2022). Parental attitudes to the outdoors therefore have an impact on the future young adult. If families do not engage in recreational visits to the outdoors, then providing OL and OE experiences at school ensures that all young people benefit from at least some outdoor play and learning experience. Where parents are fearful of outdoor environments, perhaps through lack of experience of visiting themselves, children may encourage familial visits to forests and other green spaces via the ripple effect described in Section 4.4, thus mitigating some of the wider family's fear of the unknown.

If families do not visit the outdoors due to ethnic or cultural reasons, the ripple effect can again potentially ameliorate this. If families can be encouraged to engage with the outdoor environment through their young person's experience at school, then this benefits not only the child, but the wider family.

There is of course a need for further research to determine whether these capabilities are in fact afforded through OL and OE. We also recognise that the development of the capabilities discussed here are dependent on an equity of access to OL and OE across Scotland, which has not yet been realised (see Section 5).

5. Discussion and future research recommendations

This report contributes to the nascent body of knowledge on young people's recreational engagement with nature and the outdoors.

Our primary research question was about whether OL and OE in early years has an impact on secondary school aged children and young adults' recreational use of the outdoors. We did not find a great deal of evidence from our literature search that addressed this specific question, although Liddicoat and Krasny (2014) did find that, five years after taking part in an OE residential camp during primary school, participants reported that they undertook more hiking and camping as a result of their experience. We note that a lack of longitudinal research in the literature connecting the experiences children have in ELC and primary school education with their behaviour in young adulthood makes it hard to draw conclusions about whether

young adults are motivated to make more recreational visits to the outdoors as a result of OL and OE programmes at school.

In lieu of direct evidence of links between ELC and primary OL with secondary school age and young adult behaviour, using a life course lens, we first looked at the known benefits to adults and young people as a result of nature engagement in childhood. We then identified some of the key barriers and constraints, as well as motivators, to young adults making recreational visits to the outdoors. Through an examination of the benefits that have been identified as arising from OL and OE in practice in ELC and primary education, we have identified opportunities that may reduce some of the barriers that prevent young people making recreational use of the outdoors. These opportunities (free play and active engagement with nature; social support through friends with the same OL experience; familial interest and support through the ripple effect) can potentially afford and enable young people to develop the skills, knowledge and capabilities to spend time recreationally in outdoor environments. This aligns with the Scottish Government's National Performance Framework, which aims to address how to get more people outdoors.

Remaining barriers and (in)equity of access

This report has mainly considered barriers to engagement with outdoor environments from the point of view of the young adult. Although OL and OE are firmly embedded within the educational curriculum in Scotland, it is important to acknowledge the challenges and barriers that continue to exist from the point of view of the educational practitioner, as well as more broadly across Scotland.

The capabilities we identified in Section 4.6 are supported by the concept of equity of access to OL and OE through Scotland's CfE. However, while OL and OE are fundamental components of CfE and LfS, and there are many positive examples of effective OL and OE throughout Scotland (see, for example, *Successful Approaches to Learning Outdoors*, 2022), not all schools across Scotland are currently providing the same level of experience.

Mannion et al. (2023) report results from a survey conducted by NatureScot across 19 ELC and 25 primary schools in Scotland on teaching, learning and playing outdoors. They compared findings from the same survey conducted in 2014 and found that while OL provision in ELC had increased (up to 39% of time is spent outdoors), for primary schools provision had declined from 12 minutes per pupil per week in 2014 to only 7 minutes in 2022¹. The authors also found that the amount of time spent in OL was lower in more deprived areas, and that school roll can have an impact: more time is spent outdoors when the school roll is under 100 pupils.

Practitioner confidence

Despite a wealth of good practice information and guidance available to practitioners, Mannion et al. (2023) found that many staff lack confidence in facilitating OL and LfS, particularly at primary school level. The authors discuss the need for high quality professional learning amongst practitioners in order to boost confidence and practice, and also point to the importance of supportive leadership within the school.

Practitioners worry about health and safety issues in OL and OE (Walker et al., 2021). However, in their systematic review on the association between childcare environments and

¹ Although the same survey was distributed to secondary schools only two schools responded and the results were not reported.

practice with children's physical activity levels, Martin et al. (2022) found that most of the injuries that were reported in OE settings were minor.

Lack of local knowledge

Mannion et al. (2023) report that, within Scottish primary school education, use of local green space areas has declined since 2014. While reasons for this may include barriers such as lack of time (or perceptions thereof) (Walker et al., 2021) or practitioner confidence, another contributing factor may be lack of awareness of how close local green spaces actually are. Practitioners do not always live in the same area as they work, and therefore may be unaware of local green spaces, or perceive them to be further away than they actually are. The Learning in Local Greenspace project (Munro, 2022) developed a legacy of materials to support OL, one of which is the [Greenspace Map for Outdoor Learning](#) which may enable practitioners to exploit the opportunities for OL in the local environment.

OL and OE at secondary level

In a recent report, the importance of OL to recruiting to the workforce of land-based careers in Scotland was outlined (Scottish Government, 2023). However, the observation was also made that 'there is a lack of consistency in the access of learners to opportunities to engage with learning outdoors, particularly within secondary schools' (p.3). Mannion et al. (2023) also point to the lack of evidence about quantity and quality of OL across secondary school education compared to primary and ELC settings.

A new proposed Outdoor Education Bill in Scotland may go some way to redressing this concern about equity of access to OE in secondary education. The new legislation will ensure that all young people between 12-16 years old have the opportunity to experience at least one week of residential OE. If implemented, this programme would also help to address some of the intersectionality issues noted in this report, by enabling young people from all backgrounds and genders to benefit from a similar OE experience.

Continuing to develop partnership working between public, private and third-sector organisations in Scotland's education system can also be a useful gateway to increasing the amount of time children spend outdoors. For example, existing programmes such as the John Muir Award and the Duke of Edinburgh's Award are often run through schools and their availability can go some way towards ensuring that children from all backgrounds experience a significant amount of time in outdoor environments.

A shift in the cultural norm

While these barriers are not easy to overcome, there are positive indications from the ELC sector, not only in the amount of time that is now spent outdoors, but also in that there is now a reported expectation from parents and carers that much of their children's time will be spent outdoors (Mannion et al., 2023). This indicates that a shift towards a cultural norm of OL and OE within Scotland is underway.

Future research recommendations

Given that we found only one paper that addressed our primary research question directly, we highlight the need for further research that investigates the linkages between OL and OE in ELC and primary education with recreational visits to the outdoors by young adults. Gaps in our literature review suggest particular needs for longitudinal research and more research on intersectionality.

Longitudinal research

Despite the evidence that spending time in nature as a child has been linked to multiple benefits as an adult (see Section 4.1), the specific role of childhood exposure to nature, particularly through OL and OE, remains relatively underexplored. The lack of evidence is in part due to the lack of longitudinal and long-term research on environmental education, illustrated in Figure 2 (Turtle et al., 2015; Gray & Pigott, 2018; Wells & Lekies, 2006; Beyer et al., 2015).

Smith et al. (2018) note that there is a general acceptance that one's relationship with nature develops over regular, recurring experiences in nature. As such, it would be valuable to understand how/if the benefits of OL and OE continue once the children's participation in the particular learning programme has ceased (Smith et al., 2018). We therefore recommended that future studies focus on the life course perspective of OL and OE programmes using a longitudinal approach.

There are significant challenges inherent in conducting longitudinal research, particularly involving children. It can be difficult to secure funding for long term projects, and there are many ethical considerations when participants are under the age of sixteen. However, in order to better understand the role that OL and OE play in an individual's life over time, longitudinal research needs to be undertaken. Results will help inform educational policy, to ensure that the design of OL and OE programmes maximises the likelihood and capabilities of young people to make recreational visits to the outdoors.

Figure 2 The need for longitudinal research. Source: The Authors.

Intersectional research

Intersectionality also needs to be addressed in future research. Different people and groups follow different paths from their childhood experiences, through young adulthood, to adult attitudes and behaviours (Wells & Lekies, 2006). Researchers need to recognise and explore the impact that intersecting factors such as gender, ethnicity, age and socioeconomic status (Wells & Lekies, 2006; Powers, 2020) can have. There is growing awareness of the different experiences and needs that young adult girls and boys have in outdoor public spaces (see,

for example, Girlguiding, 2020; Make Space for Girls, 2023). Considering these needs in light of other factors such as ethnic background and socioeconomic status is important and sits within the Scottish Government's commitment to getting it right for every child (GIRFEC). It is also important to conduct research taking into account the influence of the urban or rural locations in which children grow up (Turtle et al., 2015; Powers, 2020). Such research has the potential to be beneficial in ensuring that all groups are specifically targeted with outdoor opportunities that would appeal to them, which could make the impact of OL and OE more influential.

Concluding comments

This narrative literature review has examined the evidence for whether access to nature during a child's time in ELC and primary school encourages subsequent recreational visits to the outdoors by secondary school children and young adults. Whilst the review process did not return many studies addressing this topic directly, it has shed light on some of the barriers that prevent young adults from visiting the outdoors, as well as highlighting how OL and OE can help overcome some of these barriers.

Scotland's education curriculum, with its focus on LfS and outdoor play and learning is well placed to enable children and young adults to develop capabilities for recreational outdoor engagement. It is, however, important that more longitudinal research studies be conducted to better understand the effects of OL and OE on children through their life course. This will enable policy makers to ensure that OL and OE practice within ELC, primary and secondary school is maximally effective in helping foster and develop the skills, knowledge and desire in young adults to spend time outdoors.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Research protocol

Children-Nature literature synthesis protocol for Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing (JHI-C6-1)

Background: This literature synthesis forms part of a work package within the JHI-C6-1 project titled Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing funded by the Scottish Government under the Rural Affairs, Food and Environment (RAFE) Strategic Research Programme (SRP) 2022-27. The overall aim for the project is to investigate possibilities and constraints for building capacities for reciprocal nature engagement through aspects of environmental settings (type, quality), users (barriers, behaviours), mechanisms for benefit (green prescribing, OL) and investment (costs, preventative spend).

Literature Synthesis Aim: To examine whether access to nature during a child’s time in Early Learning and Childcare and Primary School encourages subsequent recreational visits to the outdoors by secondary school aged children/young adults.

This review relates to RQ4 (as listed in the SRP tender document): *“Does access to green space in early years correlate to health and wellbeing benefits later in life? Understanding of the impact that outdoor recreation in childhood has across the life course will assist policy makers in developing early years OE policy and investment”*.

Overview of approach: This narrative literature review will investigate associations between OL by pre-school and primary age pupils with subsequent recreational visits to the outdoors by secondary school aged children / young adults. Visits to the outdoors is a learned behaviour which highlights the influence of role models and a need to understand early life course (dis)engagement moments and development of associated capabilities for continued nature engagement over the life course. We propose identifying relevant factors such as gender, barriers, and opportunities.

Draft report to be submitted to relevant stakeholders for review - **Jan 2023**. (updated to March 2023 in consultation with RESAS stakeholder to account for phase 2 of literature search)

Literature Eligibility criteria:

(May need to be refined based on amount of literature identified through our search)

Criteria	Eligibility & Rationale
Population	Early Learning and Childcare and school age children/young adults <u>Rationale:</u> To include <i>children 3-18 years old</i> . This expands the focus beyond the original ‘early years’ language of the research question to reflect emerging demand among policy and practice to understand the drivers of visits to the outdoors by teenagers. Inclusion of pre-teen and teenagers additionally identifies relevant literature to inform development of the JHI-C6-1 longitudinal study of young girls’ engagement with the outdoors.
Intervention	Outdoor education/learning during pre-school/Early Learning and Childcare and Primary school <u>Rationale:</u> We focus on nature engagement associated with <i>Outdoor Learning/education during pre-school/Early Learning and Childcare and Primary school</i> (3 to ~12 [P7] years old) as this will assist policymakers in developing outdoor learning / education policy and investment (as outlined in the research question).
Outcome	Subsequent visits to the outdoors during secondary school children/young adults

	<p><u>Rationale:</u> We focus on <i>subsequent recreational visits to the outdoors among secondary school children/young adults (~12-18 years old)</i> as this aligns with the wider JHI C6-1 project and the Scottish Government's National Performance Framework which aims to get more people outdoors. Here, we are specifically interested in understanding how outdoor education/learning may be a driver for recreational visits to the outdoors by secondary school aged children / young adults.</p> <p>Exclusion: wellbeing benefit from visits to the outdoors (based on Scottish Government's general acceptance of wellbeing benefits and thus emphasis on facilitating getting people outside).</p>
Setting	<p>Green/blue spaces, rural and urban, as defined below in the following countries: United Kingdom, Ireland, Norway, The Netherlands, Belgium, Germany, Denmark, Luxemburg, France, Austria, and Poland and Finland.</p> <p><u>Rationale:</u> These countries were selected as they are within the same geographical biome as Scotland, and within Europe. Thus, they have similar green space ecology. The countries highlighted are within the temperate deciduous forest biome, with the exemption of Norway and Finland. Norway has been added due to the cultural similarities to Scotland, particularly in rural and island communities. Finland has been added due to its strong track record of in school nature time.</p> <p><u>Rationale:</u> The research has selected to focus on Europe due to the cultural similarities for engagement with nature and recreational activities. Depending on the volume of relevant literature identified, we could expand the setting criteria to include other countries (e.g. Canada, United States).</p>
Language	English
Publication Status	Published and grey literature, excluding pre-prints, editorial or opinion pieces. Depending on the volume of relevant literature we may exclude review or limit the literature to reviews only, conducting a 'review of reviews'.
Publication years	Within 5 years. Depending on the volume of relevant literature identified in initial searches, this may be modified.
Study design	Both qualitative and quantitative research. Key interest on longitudinal prospective or retrospective research.
Information Sources	<p>Web of Science – covering range of academic literature</p> <p>Scottish Government website to capture grey literature, funded reports</p>

Appendix A: Definitions

Green space	<i>Vegetated areas and blue spaces</i> in both urban and rural areas, including woodland, parks, farmland, paths and beaches and other aquatic environments that are publicly accessible (Scottish Government, 2018).
Outdoor Learning	Outdoor learning is an approach to learning embedded within the curriculum. It takes place in a range of contexts such as the school grounds, local areas, on day excursions or field trips and residential experiences. Its purposes include developing environmental understanding, encouraging physical activity, health and wellbeing and personal and social development (Education-Scotland, 2015).
Outdoor Education	Outdoor education is a distinct field of study on which educational programmes have been based since the mid-1900s. OE has been, and still is, within the purview of informal education providers and is based on shorter term, supplementary learning experiences to a student's formal schooling (Miller, 2017).
Visits to the outdoors	We operationalise visits to the outdoors per the National Performance Indicator as both everyday activities done from home or while on a Scotland-based holiday.
Pre-school / school age children/young adults	Early learning and Childcare: Children are able to go to public nursery schools in Scotland from the age of three. Primary school: Dependant on when in the year a child's birthday falls, children will attend primary school for seven years between the ages of five and 12. Secondary school: Dependant on when in the year a child's birthday falls, children will attend secondary school for up to six years between the ages of 12 and 18.
Early learning and childcare	"Early learning and childcare" means a service, consisting of education and care, of a kind which is suitable in the ordinary case for children who are under school age, regard being had to the importance of interactions and other experiences which support learning and development in a caring and nurturing setting (in Section 46 of Children and Young People (Scotland) Act 2014)

Appendix B: Search strategy keywords (greyed words = will be included only if low volume of literature as we assume we will pick up this literature through keywords for other concepts)

Green/blue space	"green" "space" OR greenspace OR "blue" "space" OR bluespace OR park OR wood OR forest OR outdoor* OR canal OR river OR burn OR stream OR lake* OR loch OR beach OR coast* OR reserve OR "local nature reserve"
School age	child* OR young person OR young people OR teenage* OR adolescent OR young OR age OR 3–18-Year-olds OR school age
OL / education	forest school OR forest kindergarten OR outdoor education OR outdoor learning OR residential experiences OR fieldtrips OR outdoor education centres OR outdoor nursery OR outdoor play and learning
Visits to the outdoors	nature engage* OR "use of outdoors" OR "visits to outdoors" OR "outdoor recreation" OR "outdoor leisure"

Appendix C: Stakeholder Engagement

Project proposal stage involved input from: RESAS; NatureScot; Public Health Scotland (PHS); Cairngorms National Park Authority (CNPA); Growing Up in Scotland (GUS).

Protocol development: RESAS and policy areas identified as relevant to use of the outdoors by pre-school / school age children/young people (Early learning and Childcare, Curriculum Development) fed into the following key protocol areas:

- Literature eligibility criteria: population, intervention, outcome
- Keyword identification
- Identifying sources of grey literature

Report: RESAS and relevant policy stakeholders involved in protocol development to contribute to:

- Output format and distribution
- Review draft report

References for Children-Nature Literature Synthesis Protocol

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Appendix 2: Key references and findings

Evidence of increased recreational visits as secondary school aged/young adult as a result of outdoor education in 3-12 year old age bracket

Reference	Location	Population	Intervention/Educational Programme	Key Findings
Liddicoat & Krasny (2014)	USA	5 th and 7 th graders, followed up at 10 th and 12 th grade	Residential outdoor environmental education	Increased participation in outdoor recreation activities, engaging in environmentally responsible behaviours

Insight of benefits of outdoor education: UK context

Reference (alphabetical)	Location	Population	Intervention/Educational Programme	Key Findings
Garip et al. (2021)	England	5–10 year olds and 13–19 year olds	School- and community-based sessions to engage with outdoor environments in London	Positive impacts on participants' nature understanding, confidence, nature connection, wellbeing, and involvement in green outdoor environments.
Harvey et al. (2020)	England	8–11 year olds	Biodiversity-focused activities carried out in school grounds over 1 year, compared to control group	Intervention group showed improvements in mood and wellbeing, and a greater connection to nature than the control group.
O'Brien & Murray (2007)	England	3-9 year olds	Weekly or fortnightly forest school sessions with changes tracked in the children over an 8-month period	Positive impacts on children in terms of their: confidence; social skills; language; communication, motivation and concentration; physical skills; and knowledge and understanding.

O'Brien et al. (2016)	UK	4-11 year olds and 14-25 year olds	4-11yrs: "Learning in Natural Environments (LINE) in England 14-25yrs: Hill Holt Wood (HHW) social enterprise providing green education for pupils excluded from school in Scotland	Interventions can encourage and enable green education which in turn has physical activity benefits. Further benefits were sensory experience; appreciation of wildlife; sense of freedom and place; and feelings of ease outdoors. Green education can also be especially important for those with additional support needs (e.g., ADHD)
Smith et al. (2018)	UK	Early years to secondary school age groups	Forest school	Positive impacts included: increased knowledge and understanding of nature and environment; improved relationship with the outdoors; pride in knowledge; and ownership of local environment. Impact from forest school can "ripple" back to home, meaning parents and teachers are more likely to engage and reduce their perceived risks.
Trapasso et al. (2018)	England	7-9 year olds	Forest school sessions compared to regular school day or day with PE	Reported an increased level of physical activity on forest school days. Findings showed differences in male and female students' preference for activities, but similar dislikes.
Traynor et al. (2022)	Scotland	Parental interviews and observations of 2-7 year olds	Nature-based ELC programmes	These programmes support cognitive, social, emotional, physical, and environmental outcomes. By engaging in various outdoor activities, urban nature based ELC can improve gross motor development, sleep duration and physical activity levels.
Turtle et al. (2015)	UK	8-11 year olds	Schools with forest school programmes compared to those without	Children who take part in a forest school programme demonstrate a more pro-environmental attitude than those who do not.

White et al. (2018)	England	7-10 year olds	Bird feeding and monitoring at school	Results demonstrated an enhanced awareness of local biodiversity and a ripple effect into family life.
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Insight of benefits of outdoor education: Outwith the UK context

Reference (alphabetical)	Location	Population	Intervention/Educational Programme	Key Findings
Alme & Reime (2021)	Norway	Kindergarten	Nature kindergartens	Nature kindergartens offer participatory situations that involve and challenge children as well as stimulating their creative play.
Ayotte-Beaudet et al. (2021)	Canada	10–12 year olds	Outdoor science lessons on school grounds	Deepened children’s learning about and engagement with the outdoors; strengthened their connection to nature and desire to protect it.
Beyer et al. (2015)	USA	10–12 year olds	Influence of urban education programme on children’s attitudes to outdoor play	Reduced fear, increased knowledge of places to play.
Gray & Pigott (2018)	Australia	14-15 year olds, followed up 30 years later	2-year wilderness studies class (equal time spent outside as inside)	Found a large proportion of participants took up occupations involving outdoor leadership and environmental stewardship.

Gregg (2009)	USA	Students of different ages across school and college	Journalling in conjunction with outdoor learning programmes	Positive impact of journalling: allowed students to reflect on personal growth and career goals, and document how outdoor learning applies to the rest of their life.
Hansen et al. (2020)	Sweden	7–12 year olds	Ecological restoration - aims to introduce importance of restoring habitats	Classes like this can address the disconnect that children feel with nature, especially at school.
Hartmeyer & Mygrind (2016)	Denmark	3 rd -5 th grade	Taught outdoors one day a week (“nature class”), followed up 5 years later	Strong cooperation and engagement in school-based social relations 5 years later.
Largo-Wight, Guardino & Hall (2020)	USA	Kindergarten	Outdoor classrooms – Two kindergarten classes over 6 weeks.	Teaching outside was reported as “feasible” and as a way for children to have health-promoting environmental exposure in school. Weather was a key barrier.
Norwood et al. (2022)	Australia	13-14 year olds	5 weeks indoor, 5 weeks outdoor lessons	Teachers found that indoor and outdoor classrooms were comparable regarding learning and engagement with learning.
Puhakka et al. (2019)	Finland	3–5 year olds	Greening of day-care yards	Increased wellbeing, motor and cognitive development, and environmental relationships.
Sääkklähti & Niemistö (2021)	Finland	2–7 year olds	Outdoor time in Early Childhood Education	Versatile environments can benefit children’s motor development. Day cares should have

				frequent outdoor play sessions in all weathers with a variety of activities for children's use.
Shanahan et al. (2019)	7 countries	Experts	Different types of nature-based intervention programmes	<p>The scale of impact varies from the population to the individual level and in the level of effort needed to achieve outcomes; a single intervention can affect people in multiple ways and, therefore, potentially improve wellbeing across a range of domains.</p> <p>Benefits – no specific outcomes in terms of children/teenagers; focus on different types of interventions and intended benefits.</p>
Tardona (2014)	USA	Elementary school (3-10 years old)	An educational outdoor programme, giving children from disadvantaged backgrounds to experience the outdoors.	Hoped outcome is that children will return with family to the park where the programme was located. Hopes for improved educational, mental and physical health. Continued research is necessary as to how to improve accessibility and appeal for low-income, racial, and ethnic minorities to National Park sites.
Taylor et al. (2022)	USA	9-10 year olds	Compared outdoor science lessons with indoor science lessons	A broader range of students were supported in the outdoor science lessons.

Relevant studies (not based on educational intervention)

Reference (alphabetical)	Location	Population	Study focus	Key findings
Beery & Jorgensen (2018)	Sweden and Norway	Adults and kindergarten children	Adult memories of childhood nature collecting experiences; observation of outdoor kindergarten	Sensory experiences of collecting help inform biodiversity knowledge
Goldstein et al. (2019)	USA	Educators, children aged 6 to 9, and their families	To test target populations' perceptions of a toolkit developed by the investigators to support engagement with environmental science practices and concepts in informal outdoor settings	The toolkit promoted participation by children and families in urban areas with science concepts and practices in various informal outdoor contexts. The promise of nature-based learning experiences applies to urban populations.
Hegetschweiler et al. (2022)	Switzerland	199 teenagers (14-18 years old) in nationwide online survey	Compare teenage to adults use and motivations for visiting urban forests	Teenagers will visit forests less than adults and have a preference for different activities, e.g. for socialising while adults cite using forests for contemplation. Further, teenagers were more likely to list disinterest and disgust as demotivators for visiting these spaces. Teenagers in the current day had less free play in forests during childhood than adults today did.
Izenstark & Middaugh (2022)	USA		Explore how the frequency of family-based nature activities develops throughout the life	The frequency and activity type of family-based nature activities (FBNA) changed significantly across the early life course. Frequency of FBNA across early life course was associated with

		“Emerging adults” (18-25 years old) with a parent/guardian	course (from 4 years old to 25 years old	individuals preferring to spend their free time outdoors and the frequency of time spent outside (especially between 7-17 years old).
Lieberman et al. (2022)	USA	Visually impaired 9–19 year olds	To understand visually impaired participant’s lived experiences during outdoor recreation	Three main themes of benefits, barriers and facilitators were reported, with results indicating that benefits from outdoor recreation can be achieved with adapted support and special programming.
Morris et al. (2011)	UK	Minority groups (protected characteristics: gender, race/ethnicity, disability, age)	Equality of access to British woodlands/Barriers experienced by various groups in accessing these spaces	A greater proportion of young people (16-24) than the general population had not visited woodlands. Young men feared being thought of as troublemakers and being moved on in these spaces. Young women’s childhood experiences of parental fears for their safety showed to be formative in regard to their attitudes concerning visiting woodlands as adults and sometimes linked to continuous anxiety about personal safety in these spaces. Physical and structural barriers, as well as socio-cultural, economic and personal barriers to visiting woodlands by people living in Britain
Oppliger et al. (2019)	Switzerland	13-22 year olds	Investigating the factors influencing teenagers’ frequency of visits to forests	Frequent forest visits during childhood, with parents or unsupervised with friends, are positively associated with more frequent visits as teenagers, as are certain leisure preferences. Minimal effects of school trips.

Prevot et al. (2018)	France	University students	Different degree students questioned about location of upbringing	Rural upbringing more likely to choose environmental degrees
Walker et al. (2021)	England	Headteachers, teachers/teaching assistants, school admin staff	Assessed the capacity for English primary schools to provide access to nature, and the opportunities and challenges of doing so – questionnaires, semi-structured interviews and GIS	Lack of government spending on education can be seen as a major constraint on schools' access to nature in England. Children's access to nature through primary schools is partially limited by spatial factors, namely the distance from natural environments. However, even when schools are in walkable proximity other factors, such as pressure of delivering the National Curriculum and teachers' lack of engagement with outdoor learning, may limit the opportunities for student's direct contact with nature.
Ward-Thompson, Aspinall & Montarzino (2008)	UK	Adults (significance of childhood experience)	Investigates the significance of childhood experience of woodlands and other green/natural places in relation to use and attitudes to such places as an adult. Survey and focus group	A strong relationship was found between frequent visits to woodlands or green spaces as a child and preparation to do so alone as an adult, not visiting frequently in childhood resulted in low likelihood of visiting as an adult. The physical and emotional benefits of access to green space were strongly reflected in childhood experience. Frequency of visits to nature as a child is a strong predictor of patterns of green space use as an adult – also associated with attitudes and behaviour.